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The Socio-demographic pattern of depression in Iraq

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122 depressed patients, 82 (67%) females and 40(33%) males were observed at the outpatient clinic in Ibin-Rushid psychiatric hospital in Baghdad. Depression affected the middle age females, married patients more frequently. 72.2% of all the patients were between 30-49 year of age. Table (1) shows the Age and sex distribution of depression.

The majority of females patients attempted suicide by nonviolent methods (medicine over-dose, poisoning while males by more violent methods (self injury, shooting). Disadvantageous family environment and recent life events were found as important factor in precipitating the illness. A female to male ratio of 2:1 in this study was attributed to hormonal and child birth influences, in addition to the facts that female are more likely to express and complain of depression than males. The married to single ratio was 5:1 for females, and 2: 1 for males. Table (2) shows the effect of the marital status on the incidence of depression.

Approximately 50% of female patients experienced at least one vulnerable provoking life events, with much lower number of males experienced such events. About two thirds of the patients had not reached post primary school

.Low literacy level observed in this study may reflect the back ground of population in Iraq. Table (3) shows the relation between depression and level of education.

Higher incidence of depression was observed in urban dwellers (84.4%).Table 4 shows the distribution of the patients between rural and urban areas. Approximately 50% of the female patients were house wife.

Table (1): Age and sex distribution of depression.

Age group	Female	Male	Total	%
20-29	6	6	12	9.8
30-39	34	16	50	41.1
40-49	28	10	38	31.1
50-59	8	6	14	11.4
60—	6	2	8	6.6
TOTAL	82	40	122	100%

Table (2): Depression and the marital status

Marital status	Female	Male	Total
Married	40	22	62(50.8%)
Single	8	12	20(16.4%)
Divorced	16	4	20(16.4%)
Widowed	12	-	12(9.8%)
Separated	6	2	8(6.6%)
Total	82	40	122

Table (3): Depression and level of education

Educational level	Female	Male	Total	%
Illiterate	16	2	18	14.7
Read write	12	2	14	11.5
Primary school	26	18	44	36
Post primary	18	12	30	24.6
University higher	10	6	16	13.2
total	82	40	122	100%

Table (4): The distribution of the patients between rural and urban areas.

	Female	Male	Total	%
Urban	69	34	103	84.5
Rural	13	6	19	15